

Soprano Saxophone

Piano

Drumset

Drumset

Drumset

Hi-hat

Thundersheet

5

S. Sax.

Pno.

Drs.

Drs.

Drs.

Hi-hat

Thu.

9

S. Sax.

Pno.

Drs.

Drs.

Drs.

Hi-hat

Thu.

12

S. Sax.

Pno.

Drs.

Drs.

Drs.

Hi-hat

Thu.

15

S. Sax.

Pno.

Drs.

Drs.

Drs.

Hi-hat

Thu.

18

S. Sax.

Pno.

Drs.

Drs.

Drs.

Hi-hat

Thu.

S. Sax. 

Pno. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Hi-hat 

Thu. 

S. Sax. 

Pno. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Hi-hat 

Thu. 

S. Sax. Pno. Drs. Drs. Drs. Hi-hat Thu.

The musical score consists of seven staves. The top staff is for S. Sax. (Soprano Saxophone) in treble clef, featuring a long note with a slur. The second staff is for Pno. (Piano) in bass clef, showing chords and a triplet. The three staves labeled 'Drs.' (Drums) are in common time, with the first staff showing a long note with a slur, the second staff showing a rhythmic pattern with eighth notes and triplets, and the third staff showing a pattern with eighth notes and a quarter note. The 'Hi-hat' staff uses 'x' marks to indicate hits. The 'Thu.' (Tuba) staff is in common time with a long note and a slur.